

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF "KEDUNG JAMBE SWIMMING POOL" TOURISM IN BAKALAN VILLAGE, PURWOSARI DISTRICT, PASURUAN REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

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The development of the village-based tourism sector requires the involvement of various stakeholders to realize sustainable management. This study aims to describe the application of *collaborative governance* in the development of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool tourism in Bakalan Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency. This study uses a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach. Data collection techniques are carried out through interviews, observations, and documentation. The research analysis uses the *collaborative governance* model proposed by Ranner which includes three stages, namely identifying obstacles and opportunities (*listening phase*), debating influence strategies (*dialogue phase*), and planning collaborative actions (*choice phase*). In addition, the success of collaboration was analyzed using Goldsmith and Kettl indicators consisting of *networked structure, commitment to a common purpose, trust among the participants, governance, access to authority, distributive accountability/responsibility, information sharing, and access to resources*. The results of the study show that the *collaborative*

governance process in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool has involved the Bakalan Village Government, BUMDes, POKDARWIS, Karang Taruna, and the local community. However, the implementation has not been running optimally. Some of the obstacles found include the absence of written regulations that bind stakeholders, weak commitment of some actors in carrying out their duties and responsibilities, limited human resources, low community participation, and lack of budget support for the development of tourism facilities and infrastructure. Nevertheless, the relationship of trust, the division of authority, and the mechanism of sharing information between stakeholders have been established quite well. Therefore, institutional strengthening, increasing human resource capacity, and clearer budget and regulatory support are needed to increase the effectiveness of collaboration in the development of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool tourism.

Keywords: *Collaborative Governance*, Tourism Development, Tourism Village, Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, Stakeholders.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is known as a country with enormous tourism potential, as reflected in the record arrival of foreign tourists which reached 12,658,048 visits between January and November 2024, the highest figure in the last five years. (BPS Statistics, n.d.) This shows Indonesia's attractiveness as a leading tourist destination in the eyes of the world. The surge in foreign tourist visits to Indonesia is a strong indicator of the rapid development of the tourism sector. This phenomenon, driven by Indonesia's natural attractions, puts governments, local governments, communities, and tourism business actors in a strategic position. They have a collective responsibility to ensure the fulfillment of travel rights for every individual. The fulfillment of this right not only contributes to the improvement of welfare, but also strengthens the bonds of friendship between nations, which ultimately support the creation of world peace. Furthermore, the optimization of the tourism sector is believed to be an effective solution in overcoming economic problems faced by developing countries, including Indonesia. Tourism is a total activity related to tourism and is multidimensional and multidisciplinary that emerges as a form of the needs of every person and country as well as interaction between tourists and local communities, fellow tourists, the Government, Regional Governments, and entrepreneurs (Presidential Regulation Number 26 of 2022). Tourism villages, which are regulated in Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 26 of 2022, are a unique model of community-based tourism development. By tapping into local potential and traditions, the tourist village offers an authentic experience for tourists. However, the sustainable development of tourist villages requires the active role of the government. The government is responsible for providing infrastructure, facilitating promotions, and ensuring professional management. This is in line with the paradigm *Governance* which emphasizes collaboration between the government, the private sector, and the community. These three pillars, as revealed by the Asurah & Wibawani in (Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², 2024), has a crucial role in driving the tourism sector. With strong synergy, tourism villages can become the driving force of the local economy, increase the country's foreign exchange, and create jobs.

According to Ansell and Gash *Collaborative Governance* is a joint decision-making process involving one or more government agencies and non-governmental institutions to implement public policies and manage public assets (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Based on this definition, *Collaborative Governance* can be understood as a cooperative effort involving various stakeholders (*Stakeholders*) in meeting the needs of an increasingly diverse community. Through this concept, it is hoped that synergy will be created between the community or community, the private sector, academics, and the government in formulating policies and developing tourism potential. In the context of this study, *Collaborative Governance* is expected to be able to be a solution in the management and development of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool tourism in Bakalan Village. Given that tourism is an integrative sector that involves many parties, its success cannot be achieved without the cooperation and support of various stakeholders (Danastry et al., 2021).

Pasuruan Regency is one of the areas located in the province of East Java, where Pasuruan is included in the strategic area in East Java. Pasuruan is also referred to as the golden triangle. Because the geographical location of Pasuruan Regency is in the middle, connecting Malang-Blitar. To the east it connects Probolinggo to Banyuwangi. It is also directly a buffer for the city of Surabaya. Pasuruan Regency also has several tours that are able to attract tourists, both cultural and natural tourism. Pasuruan is one of the regions that develops tourism as a form of effort to introduce Pasuruan to people outside the region. The Pasuruan Regency Government has also ratified PASURUAN REGENCY REGIONAL REGULATION NUMBER 4 OF 2021 CONCERNING TOURISM VILLAGES concerning the Development of Tourism Village destinations, in accordance with Article 7 letter a, covering a series of comprehensive efforts. First, community empowerment is the main foundation, ensuring active participation and direct benefits for local residents. Furthermore, the development of unique and authentic tourist attractions is a priority, attracting tourists with the cultural and natural richness of the village (Pasuruan Regency Regional Regulation No. 4 of 2021 concerning Villages, 2021). The development of adequate infrastructure, such as road access and communication networks, as well as the provision of comfortable public facilities, such as toilets and rest areas, are important to support the comfort of visitors. The construction of Tourism Village facilities is carried out in an integrated and sustainable manner, ensuring sustainability and improving service quality. The preservation of natural resources and the environment is the main concern, maintaining the beauty and sustainability of the village ecosystem. Finally, strengthening cultural elements and customs is the essence, maintaining the identity and uniqueness of the village as the main attraction for tourists.

One of the tourist destinations in Pasuruan Regency that is able to attract local and non-local tourists is the "Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool". This tour is located in Bakalan Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency. Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers, the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool was established in 2020 which was initially formed by the local BUMDES and inaugurated by the Pasuruan Regency government in 2023. The Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is a former Rest Area path that is used as a resting place for company cars and then transformed into an attractive destination. Seeing the potential that can support the progress of Bakalan Village, in this tourism development the government uses *collaborative governance*, which in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool involves various actors ranging from the government to the community itself. The youth organization assisted by the Kedung Jambe Village Government continues to build the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. However, the construction process did not go according to what was expected. This is due to the lack of actors involved in the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool and also the lack of communication by the parties involved so that the existing management does not run well. The awareness of the local

community in supporting the establishment and maintaining the tourism is also said to be lacking, as can be seen from the community's awareness in maintaining the cleanliness of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. Based on the results of interviews with tour managers, visitors to the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool in 2024 - now only reach 10-15 people per day compared to the initial 2023 inauguration can reach approximately 100 people per day, which means that this shows that the number of tourists visiting the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is decreasing every year. Many facilities and infrastructure at the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool have been damaged and only a few are still in use. In this case, the role of the youth organization in maintaining facilities and infrastructure is not optimal. This is what causes tourists to be reluctant to visit the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. With this, the implementation of *collaborative governance* in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is still experiencing obstacles, especially the lack of involvement in the role of stakeholders which is still said to be not optimal."

By concept *Collaborative Governance*, explained that the need to collaborate arises from the existence of a relationship of interdependence between parties. According to (Ansell & Gash, 2008) *Collaborative governance* It can also be described as a process that involves shared norms and mutually beneficial interactions between actors *Governance*. Through perspective *Collaborative Governance*, the concept is expected to be able to be a problem solver in tourism management and development. Research *Collaborative Governance* has been carried out in the field of tourism, but the identification of the process and the success in its development have not been done much (Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², 2024).

According to Ranner in (Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², 2024), process

Collaborative Governance It involves three stages of collaboration in governance, namely:

1. **Identifying Barriers and Opportunities (Listening Phase)** At this stage, the collaborating stakeholders identify various obstacles that may be encountered during the collaborative process. Each stakeholder explains the problems faced, and the other stakeholders listen to each problem that is presented.
2. **Debating the Influence Strategy (Dialogue Phase)** At this stage, the stakeholders involved discuss the barriers that have been identified in the first phase. Discussions include the most effective steps to solve the problem and identify parties who can support the problem-solving process.
3. **Planning Collaborative Actions (Optional Phase)** At this stage, stakeholders begin to plan the implementation of the strategies that have been discussed earlier. This includes the first step in the process of collaboration between stakeholders, namely the government, the private sector, and the community. In addition, the identification of measurements of each process carried out and the determination of

steps to maintain the sustainability of collaboration in the long term.

From the stages of the collaboration process put forward by Ranner, Goldsmith and Kettl (2009, n.d.) To improve by mentioning that there are important things that can be used as a benchmark for the success of a collaboration in *Governance*, namely: *Networked Structure, Commitment to a Common Purpose, Trust Among The Participants, Governance, Access to Authority, Distributive Accountability/Responsibility, Information Sharing, Access to Resource* (Irawan, 2016).

Based on the description of the concept presented above, the focus of this research is how the process of developing the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool in the concept of *collaborative governance*. This study aims to describe how *collaborative governance* in the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Collaborative Governance

Collaborative Governance has emerged as an important approach in public administration to address complex public issues that cannot be solved by a single actor. According to Ansell and Gash (2008), Collaborative Governance is a governing arrangement in which one or more public agencies directly engage non-state stakeholders in a collective decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and deliberative, aimed at making or implementing public policy and managing public programs or assets.

The concept emphasizes cooperation among government institutions, private sectors, communities, and other stakeholders to achieve common goals. Through collaborative governance, stakeholders can share resources, responsibilities, authority, and information to improve policy implementation and public service outcomes.

In tourism development, collaborative governance plays a crucial role because tourism activities involve multiple actors with different interests and resources. Effective collaboration can encourage sustainable tourism management and improve local economic development.

2.2 Tourism Development

Tourism development refers to a planned effort to improve tourism destinations through the utilization of natural, cultural, and human resources while ensuring environmental sustainability and community welfare. Tourism is recognized as one of the strategic sectors contributing significantly to economic growth, employment opportunities, and regional development.

According to Presidential Regulation Number 26 of 2022, tourism development should involve various stakeholders and be carried out through sustainable and integrated management. Therefore, cooperation among government agencies, tourism businesses, and local communities is essential to achieve successful tourism development.

2.3 Tourism Village Development

A tourism village is a rural area that possesses tourism attractions based on local culture, natural resources, traditions, and community activities. Tourism village development aims to create economic opportunities for local communities while preserving cultural values and environmental sustainability.

In Indonesia, tourism villages have become one of the government's priorities in promoting community-based tourism. The success of tourism village development depends on stakeholder participation, institutional support, infrastructure availability, and community empowerment.

2.4 Collaborative Governance Process

This study adopts the collaborative governance process model proposed by Ranner. According to Ranner, collaborative governance consists of three phases:

a. Listening Phase

The listening phase focuses on identifying barriers, opportunities, stakeholder interests, and existing problems. Stakeholders communicate their concerns and expectations while listening to one another's perspectives.

b. Dialogue Phase

The dialogue phase involves discussions among stakeholders regarding identified issues. Through dialogue, stakeholders exchange ideas, negotiate interests, and formulate alternative solutions to overcome existing challenges.

c. Choice Phase

The choice phase refers to the process of determining collaborative actions and strategies. Stakeholders jointly formulate plans, allocate responsibilities, and establish mechanisms to ensure the sustainability of collaboration.

2.5 Indicators of Collaborative Governance Success

To assess the effectiveness of collaboration, this study uses the indicators proposed by Goldsmith and Kettl (2009), namely:

1. Networked Structure
2. Commitment to a Common Purpose
3. Trust among Participants
4. Governance

5. Access to Authority
6. Distributive Accountability/Responsibility
7. Information Sharing
8. Access to Resources

These indicators provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating the success of collaborative governance in tourism development.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive qualitative research approach. Qualitative research is appropriate because it enables the researcher to explore and understand the collaborative governance process in the development of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool Tourism in Bakalan Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency.

Research Location

The research was conducted at Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool Tourism, located in Bakalan Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency, East Java, Indonesia.

Research Focus

The focus of this study is the implementation of collaborative governance in the development of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool Tourism. The analysis is based on:

1. The collaborative governance process proposed by Ranner:
 - Listening Phase
 - Dialogue Phase
 - Choice Phase
2. Collaborative governance success indicators proposed by Goldsmith and Kettl:
 - Networked Structure
 - Commitment to a Common Purpose
 - Trust among Participants
 - Governance
 - Access to Authority
 - Distributive Accountability/Responsibility
 - Information Sharing
 - Access to Resources

Research Informants

Informants were selected using purposive sampling techniques. The selected informants were individuals who had direct involvement and understanding of tourism development activities.

The informants consisted of:

- Head of Bakalan Village
- BUMDes Management
- POKDARWIS Members
- Karang Taruna Representatives
- Local Community Members
- Visitors of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool Tourism

Data Collection Techniques

Data were collected through:

1. Observation

Observation was conducted to examine tourism facilities, tourism activities, stakeholder participation, and the overall condition of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool Tourism.

2. Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants to obtain in-depth information regarding stakeholder collaboration and tourism development processes.

3. Documentation

Documentation was collected from village records, tourism development reports, photographs, meeting minutes, organizational documents, and other relevant archives.

Data Analysis Technique

Data were analyzed using the interactive model developed by Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña, consisting of:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Condensation
3. Data Display
4. Conclusion Drawing and Verification

Data Validity

The validity of the data was ensured through source triangulation and technique triangulation. Source triangulation was conducted by comparing information from different informants, while technique triangulation involved comparing findings obtained through interviews, observations, and documentation.

Ethical Considerations

All participants were informed about the objectives of the study and voluntarily agreed to participate. The confidentiality of informants and research data was maintained throughout the research process.

4.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In a study entitled "*Collaborative Governance* in the Development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool in Bakalan Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency," the author obtained results that are in accordance with the collaboration model proposed by Ranner in (Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², 2024) This model is divided into three main phases or three stages that aim to see the achievements of each of these stages, which are as follows:

"1. Identifying Barriers and Opportunities (Listening Phase)

This phase is a phase of listening to each other about problems and opportunities to be able to take advantage of every problem conveyed by each stakeholder (Tua & Sihaloho, 2022). At this early stage, the originator of the idea in developing the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool was a member of the Bakalan Village Bumdes. The Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool used to be a former Rest Area, often used by local youth to relax in the afternoon. With this, the youth took the initiative to make the pond a tourist attraction. The Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is suitable for development which can be useful for the progress of Bakalan Village itself, besides that the beautiful scenery and cool atmosphere even though during the day are very suitable for tourists to unwind here. However, the initial obstacle in the development of this tourism is the lack of special attention from the local Village Government such as financing in the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, causing the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool to stop building for some time. This has an impact on the number of tourists who visit the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is still small. The lack of supporting facilities and infrastructure such as insufficient seating, the lack of availability of stalls that sell makes people reluctant to visit the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. In the early stages of the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, the only people who are often involved in this collaboration process are the Bakalan Village Youth Organization and the Bakalan Village Government. This is also one of the reasons why the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool has not run optimally. The results of identification and analysis are very important as the basis for the preparation of strategies and development plans for the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool which can later be used as recommendations and considerations by the village government.

2. Debating Influence Strategies (Dialogue Phase)

This phase is carried out after passing the first phase where the problem has been identified, then taking effective steps for the problem (Tua & Sihaloho, 2022). After the problem is identified as explained above in the first phase, the next step taken by the Bakalan Village Government is to conduct deliberations with the Bakalan

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Village Bumdes and several Bakalan Village officials. In this dialogue phase, the Bakalan Village Government saw the activeness of the youth of Bakalan Village so that the Bakalan Village Government formed a POKDARWIS (Tourism Awareness Group) to help during the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. In addition, the Bakalan Village Government also involved the Bakalan village Youth Organization in the process of developing the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. The Bakalan Village Government hopes that with the main stakeholders between BUMDES and POKDARWIS in an effort to develop the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, it can run according to what will be planned later.

3. *Collaborative Actions Plan (Optional Phase)*

After carrying out the first and second phases, the stakeholders then plan on the implementation of the strategies that have been discussed previously. The first step taken is that the stakeholders or policy makers involved begin to plan for the implementation of each strategy that has been discussed (Tua & Sihaloho, 2022). Collaborative action planning from the implementation of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool construction and development program is part of this stage. The first step taken at this stage is to involve stakeholders in the tourism development planning process. This plan is prepared systematically which contains the main tasks and functions of the stakeholders involved. For example, POKDARWIS as a tourism manager, Karang Taruna as a security guard and supervision of facilities in the tourist area, Bumdes as the management of village original income (PAD), village communities as a support for tourism by forming sales stalls provided in tourist areas, and the Bakalan Village Government which continues to provide briefings for further planning.

After conducting the stage analysis process *Collaborative Governance* according to the stages presented by Ranner in (Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², 2024), the next step is to assess the success of the implementation of the collaboration process in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool in Bakalan Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency. The analysis is an indicator of success in the process *Collaborative Governance* presented by Goldsmith and Kettl (2009, n.d.), here's the explanation:

a. Networked Structure (Struktur Jaringan) Networked Structure It is a structured relationship between agencies that correspond to each other and collectively reflect the elements of the network being handled. In relation to each other, they do not rule each other (hierarchy) or dominate one over the other. All parties have equal rights, obligations, responsibilities, authority, and opportunities for accessibility in achieving common goals (Tua & Sihaloho, 2022). In the results of this study, it can be seen that there is no hierarchy that occurs in the process *Collaborative Governance* development of Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool. The collaboration that occurs is only limited to mutual agreement without a written agreement. Implementation of collaborations involved in the process *Collaborative Governance* The development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is the Bakalan Village Government, POKDARWIS Bakalan, the Bakalan Village Youth Organization, Bakalan BUMDes, and the local community who have sales stalls in the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool tourist area. At the beginning of the collaboration process, the

stakeholders involved in carrying out the tasks went well and according to the directions, but as time went by, the tasks that should be carried out by each party involved were not carried out as they should.

b. Commitment to a Common Purpose Commitment to a common goal is an important reason why a network must exist, because to achieve a commitment with positive goals carried out together. The commitments that are established must not take sides only with one of the stakeholders, the commitments that are established in the collaboration process must be for the common good through a common solution. With this, the researcher obtained data that the commitments established between stakeholders and each other did not run in accordance with the vision and mission that had been determined at the beginning (Rivelino 1, 1979). The commitment of the Bakalan Village Government to the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool by evaluating the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool with other stakeholders, the evaluation is carried out at least 1x a month. POKDARWIS as a tourism manager who is also in charge of the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool has conducted deliberations with other stakeholders on how the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool is better known and in demand by local and non-local communities, for example by creating social media accounts such as Instagram and Facebook as well as creating unique photo spots, *Sands Outbond*, and *Games*. BUMdes as the management of regional original revenue (PAD) is committed to providing rates for entrance tickets to the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool and rates for boat rentals. However, the Bakalan Village Youth Organization, which is supposed to be the security guard and supervision of the facility, is not fully committed to the task given, this can be seen from the damage to several photo spots and the lack of maintenance of the arena *Games*. Not only that, the BUMDes that have been scheduled to guard the tourism are not run properly, this is because there are some who also work in other places. People who also do not open sales stalls every day.

a. Trust Among the Participants Trust between stakeholders is a professional or social relationship, and the belief that participants trust information or efforts from other stakeholders in a network to achieve a common goal. So in this case, every stakeholder must trust each other because it is a form of professional relationships that are established to achieve the success of the implementation of collaborative governance (Irawan, 2016). The collaborative process in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool must be established between the actors involved, namely the Bakalan Village Government, the Bakalan Village POKDARWIS, the Bakalan Village Youth Organization, the Bakalan BUMDes, and the local community. The collaboration that is carried out has begun to establish trust between stakeholders with each other. Stakeholders have good personal relationships to achieve common goals and common interests that have become the focus of each actor involved. The stakeholders involved must have mutual trust, if they are suspicious of each other, slander evidence that collaboration is no longer healthy (Pramesona, n.d.). With this, the collaboration in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool already has a sense of trust among stakeholders.

b. **Governance** *Governance* is a relationship of mutual trust between the actors *Governance* or government. In addition, there are rules that are mutually agreed upon by each stakeholder, and there is freedom to determine how collaboration is carried out. In this case, governance can be said to be *Governance* if there is clarity on who is a member and who is not a member. *Governance* in concept *Collaborative Governance* used as a measure of success. In the collaborative process of developing the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, it is not explained about the membership structure accompanied by binding legal rules. The collaboration process is carried out only in accordance with the roles and duties of each stakeholder without any written regulations (Risanti, F., & Winarni, n.d.). According to DelSelve in (Ashido et al., 2022), it is said that *Governance* must have limits, rules that regulate sanctions in the course of a collaboration. However, in this collaboration process, there are no regulations that contain restrictions on members' behavior with the threat that they will be expelled if they behave deviantly. Each stakeholder is given the freedom to assist the collaborative process in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool but still refers

to mutual agreement. The support of stakeholders without conflict in achieving the goals is still said to be not optimal, as can be seen from the limited number of human resources who manage the tourism as well as the level of public awareness that is still lacking and the lack of financial resources allocated in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool.

a. **Access to Authority** Access to authority is the availability of clear and widely accepted measures or provisions of procedures. So, there are clear rules of authority and are accepted by each stakeholder to carry out their roles according to their authority (Denny Irawan, 2017)(Irawan, 2016). In the context of the collaboration that occurred during the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, the stakeholders involved already understood how the procedure was and knew their respective duties and roles so that there was no overlap of authority.

b. **Distributive Accountability/Responsibility** The division of accountability/responsibility is the arrangement, management, management together with stakeholders and sharing responsibilities and decision-making to all network members to achieve the desired goals. Thus, in collaborative governance each stakeholder (including the public) must be involved in policy decision-making and obtain a clear division of responsibilities (Muhamad Firdaus¹, Michelle Isabella², 2022). The collaborative process in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, the Bakalan Village Government has divided the tasks and roles of each stakeholder according to their fields. The distribution of accountability by the village government is in accordance with the responsibility of each stakeholder. The meeting held by the Bakalan Village Government once a month as a forum for discussion is expected to be attended by all stakeholders in the evaluation. However, the reality is that not all stakeholders participated in the evaluation. This leads to a lack of accountability sharing because one of the stakeholders is less participating.

c. Information Sharing Sharing information is easy access for members, privacy protection, and limited access for non-members as long as it is acceptable to all parties. So that in collaborative government, there must be clear information sharing, and easy access to information can be obtained for each stakeholder (Risanti, F., & Winarni, n.d.). The collaboration in the development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool already has ease of access to information. POKDARWIS as a tourism manager has conducted a communication forum with other stakeholders and discussed the extent of the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool and what obstacles occurred. Furthermore, the results of the discussion were presented during the evaluation conducted by the Bakalan village government once a month. Although the evaluation is not routinely conducted face-to-face on a monthly basis, stakeholders can see the progress through social media. In this case, information sharing in the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool has been carried out by each stakeholder.

d. Access to Resources Access to resources is the availability of financial, technical, human, and other resources needed to achieve network goals. So, there must be clarity and availability of resources for each stakeholder involved. A program or activity can run when supported by resources, especially financial and human availability (Irawan, 2016). In this case, the lack of resources in developing tourism arises because the awareness of the

surrounding community is still quite lacking, for example in maintaining the cleanliness of tourist attractions. Currently, human resources are only limited to POKDARWIS. BUMDes that should be actively involved in supporting the tourism development process are also still not active. Limited funds are also an important resource in this development process, inadequate infrastructure causes tourists to be reluctant to visit, which can be the impact of a lack of income to repair damaged facilities, so it requires financial assistance from the government and the private sector.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research entitled "*Collaborative Governance* in the Development of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool in Bakalan Village, Kapas District, Pasuruan Regency" it can be concluded that in the development process there has been a collaborative process between stakeholders who support each other but have not been fully successful. This is based on an analysis of eight factors that measure the success of collaboration according to gold and semith (2009, n.d.) What is not achieved is the absence of official written regulations that bind the collaboration process carried out, commitments in achieving goals that are not carried out by all stakeholders involved, limited human resources and a lack of funds to build infrastructure. Based on the results of the research description and drawing

conclusions, the researcher provides suggestions for consideration in carrying out the collaboration process in the future. To support the success of the development process of the Kedung Jambe Swimming Pool, it is necessary to increase the socialization of tourism awareness and charm to all people in Bakalan Village, the development of POKDARWIS carried out by the Tourism Office, the restructuring of tourism managers for the renewal of human resources, the village government pays special attention to supporting the progress of village potential, such as providing a special budget.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

2009, S. G. and D. F. K. (n.d.). *Uncovering the Power of Networks*.
<https://www.brookings.edu/books/unlocking-the-power-of-networks/>

Ansell, C., & Gash, A. (2008). Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543-571.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum032>

Ashido, A., Panangian, G., Accounting, P. S., Economics, F., & Brawijaya, U. (2022). *CORPORATE GOVERNANCE SCORECARD AT PT . 1(1)*, 110-121.

BPS Statistics. (n.d.). *Number of Foreign Tourist Visits per Month to Indonesia by Entrance, 2008 - present (Visits), 2024*.
<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table?subject=561&sortBy=date%2Ctitle&sortOrder=desc%2Casc>

Danastry, A. G., Kurniawan, T., Indonesia, U., & Barat, J. (2021). *Scientific Journal of Public Administration (JIAP) Collaborative Governance on Fixed Broadband Network Penetration in Indonesia*. 7(2), 158-163.

Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², J. (2024). *Collaborative Governance in the Development of Tourism "Bendo Reservoir" in Bendo Village, Kapas District, Bojonegoro Regency*. 6(3), 2624-2637.
<https://doi.org/10.47476/reslaj.v6i3.6280>

Irawan, D. (2016). *(Descriptive Study of Collaborative Government Processes in Air Pollution Control in the City of Surabaya)*. 1-11.

Muhamad Firdaus¹, Michelle Isabella², N. S. N. (2022). *COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE AS A STEP TO DEVELOP TOURISM IN KARIMUN REGENCY*. 1(3), 460-465.

Pasuruan Regency Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2021 concerning Villages. (2021). *Regional Regulation (Perda) of Pasuruan Regency Number 4 of 2021 concerning Tourism Villages*. 1965.

Presidential Regulation Number 26 of 2022. (2022). *The President's Cross-Sector Strategic on the Third Amendment*. 132450, 132450-132456.

Pramesona, B. (n.d.). *Governance*.

- Risanti, F., & Winarni, F. (2018). T. K. K. D. P. D. W. W. D. K. I. K. B. (n.d.). *COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WUKIRSARI TOURISM VILLAGE IN IMOIRI DISTRICT, BANTUL REGENCY*.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/COLLABORATIVE-GOVERNANCE-DALAM-PENGEMBANGAN-DESA-DI-Risanti-Winarni/a949d932eb849247964c6e1c4aabe960f387b53e#related-papers>
- Rivelino 1, A. H. G. 2. (1979). *COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN PUBLIC POLICY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF HANDLING COVID-19 IN JAKARTA*. 13(1).
- Tua, N., & Sihaloho, P. (2022). *Collaborative Governance in Flood Management in Medan City*. *Sci*. 6, 161-174.
- 2009, S. G. and D. F. K. (n.d.). *Uncovering the Power of Networks*.
<https://www.brookings.edu/books/unlocking-the-power-of-networks/>
- Ansell, C., & Gash, A. (2008). Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543-571.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum032>
- Ashido, A., Panangian, G., Accounting, P. S., Economics, F., & Brawijaya, U. (2022). *CORPORATE GOVERNANCE SCORECARD AT PT*. 1(1), 110-121.
- BPS Statistics. (n.d.). *Number of Foreign Tourist Visits per Month to Indonesia by Entrance, 2008 - present (Visits), 2024*.
<https://www.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table?subject=561&sortBy=date%2Ctitle&sortOrder=desc%2Casc>
- Danastry, A. G., Kurniawan, T., Indonesia, U., & Barat, J. (2021). *Scientific Journal of Public Administration (JIAP) Collaborative Governance on Fixed Broadband Network Penetration in Indonesia*. 7(2), 158-163.
- Della Dwi Nanda¹, Ahmad Suprastiyo², J. (2024). *Collaborative Governance in the Development of Tourism "Bendo Reservoir" in Bendo Village, Kapas District, Bojonegoro*

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